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● New records of the subtribe *Theclina* from China with taxonomic notes (Lepidoptera, Lycaenidae, *Theclinae*)

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Abstract: The following five taxa belonging to the subtribe *Theclina* are recorded from China for the first time: *Inomataozephyrus syla* (Kollar, 1844), *Inomataozephyrus assamicus* (Tytler, 1915), *Euaspa hishikawai* Koiwaya, 2002, *Teratozephyrus arisanus kachinus* Koiwaya, 2000 and *Neozephyrus uedai kachinus* Koiwaya, 2002. *Chrysozephyrus fujiokai* Koiwaya, 2000 is recorded from Guangxi for the first time. *Howarthia jianyilingi* S.-Y. Huang, 2021 is recorded from North Vietnam for the first time and the male is discovered. All the adults and the genitalia of certain species are illustrated.

Keywords: *Theclini*, Oriental Realm, taxonomy

● 中国产线灰蝶亚族新纪录与相关分类学注解（鳞翅目，灰蝶科，线灰蝶亚科）

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摘要: 本文记述了如下 5 个中国新纪录之线灰蝶亚族分类单元：喜马拉雅金灰蝶 *Inomataozephyrus syla* (Kollar, 1848)、铈金灰蝶 *Inomataozephyrus assamicus* (Tytler, 1915)、菱川钶灰蝶 *Euaspa hishikawai* Koiwaya, 2002、阿里山铁灰蝶缅甸亚种 *Teratozephyrus arisanus kachinus* Koiwaya, 2000 及上田翠灰蝶缅甸亚种 *Neozephyrus uedai kachinus* Koiwaya, 2002。藤冈金灰蝶 *Chrysozephyrus fujiokai* Koiwaya, 2000 被首次记录于广西省。大围山何华灰蝶 *Howarthia jianyilingi* S.-Y. Huang, 2021 被首次记录于越南北部，其雄性亦被首次记载。本文图示了文中涉及的所有成虫与部分生殖器。

关键词: 线灰蝶族，东洋区，分类学

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● Introduction

Theclina is one of the most popular group among lycaenid collectors in China and Japan. Members of the subtribe are usually referred as “Zephyrus” hairstreaks and the characters have been well summarized by Koiwaya (2007). In the past two decades, the expeditions conducted by different Chinese researchers in Southwest and South China revealed several new discoveries on the members of the subtribe Theclina which have not been reported yet, and the present paper is dedicated to report them.

● Material and methods

Specimens examined are deposited in the following institutional and private collections: the research collection of Si-Yao Huang (CHSY), Zhuhai, China; the research collection of Hao Huang (CHH), Qingdao, China; the Institute of Plateau Biology of Xizang Aotonomous Region (IPBX), Lhasa, China; the Leibniz Institute for the Analysis of Biodiversity Change, Zoological Research Museum Alexander Koenig (ZFMK, former Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig), Bonn, Germany and South China Agricultural University (SCAU), Guangzhou, China. Photos of adults, except for the specimens in CHH which were provided by Hao Huang, were taken by a Sony DSC-RX100 v1.00 camera or a Panasonic DC-G91 camera. Abdomens were removed and macerated in hot 10% NaOH or KOH solution for examination of male and female genitalia. Photos of genitalia were taken under a Keyence VHX-2000 digital microscope and a Keyence VHX-5000 digital microscope. Adult and genitalia photos were all processed by Adobe Photoshop CS5 ® software. Terminology follows Koiwaya (2007). New records are marked with an asterisk (*). Abbreviation: HT = Holotype.

Label data. For the holotype label citations, information provided in quotation marks is transcribed verbatim. Different labels are separated by a forward slash (“/”) while the different lines of the same label are separated by a vertical bar (“|”). Any additional data are provided in square brackets.

● Results

Inomataozephyrus syla (Kollar, 1848) 喜马拉雅金灰蝶

Figs. 1, 2

Thecla syla Kollar, 1848: 414, pl. 4, figs. 7 & 8.

Chrysozephyrus syla Kollar: Shirôzu & Yamamoto 1956: 389, pl. 38, fig. 48; pl. 70, figs. 51a-e; pl. 83, figs. 28a-c.

Neozephyrus syla: Howarth 1957: 267, 278, fig. 40.

Material examined. 1 male, 1 female, 31. VIII. 2021, Jilong, S Xizang, SW China (IPBX).

Diagnosis. Superficially *Inomataozephyrus syla* can be distinguished from *I. assamicus* by the combination of the following characters: 1) in males, the black marginal band on upperside is of the same width on both wings, while in the latter the band on hindwing is much narrower than that of forewing and 2) in females, the purplish blue suffusion on hindwing upperside is much less extensive.

Distribution. China (S Xizang)*, Afghanistan, India & Nepal.

Inomataozephyrus assamicus (Tytler, 1915) 银金灰蝶

Fig. 3

Zephyrus assamica Tytler, 1915: 130.

Neozephyrus assamicus: Howarth 1957: 268, 278, fig. 41.

Chrysozephyrus assamicus: Koiwaya et al. 2004: 91–94, figs. 76–105.

Material examined. 1 female, 23. VII. 2017, Motuo, SE Xizang, SW China, leg. Si-yao Huang (CHH, ex CHSY).

Diagnosis. Superficially the female of *Inomataozephyrus assamicus* can be distinguished from *I. syla* by the more extensive purplish blue suffusion on hindwing upperside.

Remarks. This species was also recorded from NW Yunnan last year but has not been formerly reported (Hao Huang pers. comm.). However, currently no specimen from Yunnan is available for the author.

Distribution. China (SE Xizang & NW Yunnan)*, Nepal, India, Myanmar & Vietnam.

FIGURES 1–3. Adults of *Inomataozephyrus* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 1 & 2 in IPBX; 3 in CHH. Left row: dorsal side; Right row: ventral side.

***Euaspa hishikawai* Koiwaya, 2002 菱川轭灰蝶**

Figs. 4, 5 & 12

Euaspa hishikawai Koiwaya, 2002a: 8, figs. 22–25, 50, 60; Koiwaya 2007: 123, figs. 57–1–7.**Material examined.** 2 males, 14. V. 2019, Mt. Ailao, Xinning, Yunnan, SW China, leg. Song-yun Lang (CHSY & CHH).**Diagnosis.** Superficially the male of *Euaspa hishikawai* is reminiscent of *E. koizumii* Koiwaya, 2002, *E. nosei* Koiwaya, 2002, *E. mikamii* Koiwaya, 2002 and *E. nishimurai* Koiwaya, 2002 and can be distinguished from them by the straighter forewing termen from cell 2 to apex. In male genitalia, *E. hishikawai* is only reminiscent of *E. motokii* Koiwaya, 2002 by the shape of the distal section of uncus, but can be distinguished from it by the broader apex and lateral triangular protrusion.**Distribution.** China (SC Yunnan)*, India, Laos & Vietnam.***Teratozephyrus arisanus kachinus* Koiwaya, 2000 阿里山铁灰蝶缅甸亚种**

Fig. 6

Teratozephyrus arisanus kachinus Koiwaya, 2000c: 53, 61, figs. 9–12; Koiwaya 2007: 158, figs. 84–10 & 11.**Material examined.** 1 female, 4. VIII. 2021, Gongshan, Yunnan, SW China, leg. Si-yao Huang (CHSY).**Diagnosis.** Superficially the female of *Teratozephyrus arisanus kachinus* is reminiscent of *T. arisanus picquenardi* (Oberthür, 1914) and can be distinguished from it by the separated discal cell bar and postdiscal band, and the much narrower submarginal band on hindwing underside.**Distribution.** China (W Yunnan)*, Myanmar.***Neozephyrus uedai kachinus* Koiwaya, 2002 上田翠灰蝶缅甸亚种**

Fig. 7

Neozephyrus uedai kachinus Koiwaya, 2002b: 8, figs. 21–24; Koiwaya 2007: 184, figs. 105–4–8.**Material examined.** 1 female, 9. VIII. 2018, Mt. Ailao, Yunnan, SW China, leg. Si-yao Huang (CHH, ex CHSY).**Diagnosis.** Superficially the female of *Neozephyrus uedai kachinus* can be distinguished from that of the nominate subspecies by the less developed metallic purple area and the larger postdiscal orange patches on forewing and the less reddish ground color on the underside of both wings.**Distribution.** China (SC Yunnan)*, Myanmar & Vietnam.***Chrysozephyrus fujiokai* Koiwaya, 2000 藤冈金灰蝶**

Figs. 8 & 13

Chrysozephyrus sikkimensis fujiokai Koiwaya, 2000a: 12, 16, figs. 28–33.*Chrysozephyrus fujiokai*: Koiwaya 2003: 9, 11, figs. 38–44, 68, 69; Koiwaya 2007: 217, figs. 134–1–12; H. Huang 2019: 212, figs. 103, 209I.**Material examined.** 2 males, 2. VII. 2002, Mt. Cenwanglaoshan, Guangxi, S China (SCAU).**Diagnosis.** Superficially *Chrysozephyrus fujiokai* is reminiscent of *C. sikkimensis* (Howarth, 1957) and *C. haradai* Koiwaya, 2000, but can be distinguished from the latter two species by the more elongated valvae in male genitalia.**Distribution.** China (Guangxi)*, Guizhou & Sichuan).

FIGURES 4–7. Adults of *Theclina* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 4 & 6 in CHSY; 5 & 7 in CHH. Left row: dorsal side; Right row: ventral side.

FIGURES 8–11. Adults of *Theclina* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 8 in SCAU; 9 in ZFMK, 10 & 11 in CHH. Left row: dorsal side; Right row: ventral side.

FIGURE 12 & 13. Male genitalia of *Theclina* spp. Depositories of the specimens: 12 in CHSY, 13 in SCAU.

14

15

FIGURE 14 & 15. Genitalia of *Howarthia jianyinglingi*. Depositories of the specimens: **14** in CHH, **15:** HVN02 in CHH; Lep0050241 in ZFMK.

FIGURE 16 & 17. Female genitalia of *Howarthia jianyilingi*. Depositories of the specimens: 16 in CHH, 17 in ZFMK.

***Howarthia jianyilingi* S.-Y. Huang, 2021** 大围山何华灰蝶

Figs. 9–11, 14–17

Howarthia jianyilingi Huang, 2021: 35, Figs. 1, 2, 9, 10 & 15.

Material examined. Holotype: female, handwritten label “16-VII-2016 | 屏边 大围山 | leg 赵新杰” / printed label “CHINA: Yunnan Province, Honghe | Hani & Yi Autonomous Prefecture, | Pingbian County, Mt. Dawei, | 16. VII. 2016, Xin-jie Zhao leg.” / printed red label “HOLOTYPE | *Howarthia jianyilingi* Huang, | 2021” / printed label “ZFMK | Lep153600” / printed label “ZFMK | genprep | Lep0050241” (ZFMK). 1 male, 1 female, VI. 2024, Hagiang, Vietnam, leg. local collector (CHH, ex CHSY).

Diagnosis. Superficially *Howarthia jianyilingi* is reminiscent of *H. veneta* Hasegawa & Saito, 2020, *H. kimurai* Koiwaya, 2002 and *H. watanebei* Koiwaya, 1993, and can be distinguished from the latter three species by the combination of following characters: 1) On underside of hindwing, the postdiscal band in space 1c is shifted inwards, while in the congeners that section of the postdiscal band is shifted outwards and closer to the orange spot at tornus. 2) On upperside of forewing in male, the marginal black band is similar in width as *H. veneta*, and narrower than *H. kimurai*. Since the male of *H. watanebei* is unknown, the comparison of male genitalia is made with *H. veneta* and *H. kimurai*. In male genitalia, *H. jianyilingi* differs from *H. veneta* and *H. kimurai* in the more slender uncus with shorter distal bifurcation and the broader ampulla in valvae in lateral view. In female genitalia, *H. jianyilingi* differs from *H. veneta*, *H. kimurai* and *H. watanebei* in having a much narrower posterior distal section of lamellae antevaginalis with the two distal processes reduced to denticles, while in the latter three species the two distal processes are well-developed and longer.

Remarks. 1) The diagnosis of *H. jianyilingi* has been modified based on more material reported in the present study. 2) Huang (2021) suggested that the male of *H. kimurai* from Sapa, North Vietnam illustrated in Koiwaya (2004; 2007) and Hasegawa & Saito (2020) might actually be the male of *H. jianyilingi*, but with the discovery of the true male of this species in the present study, it is clear that *H. kimurai* sensu Koiwaya (2004; 2007) and Hasegawa & Saito (2020) is not conspecific with *H. jianyilingi*, and its true identity requires further studies based on more material. 3) The Vietnamese female has a larger lamellae antevaginalis in ventral view and stronger sclerotisation on the posterior end of ductus bursae, compared with that in the holotype, while other features remain the same. However the author believes that such differences are more likely related to individual variation, since the most important feature, the denticle-like posterior distal processes, is the same in both individuals, therefore the Vietnamese female is here still identified as *H. jianyilingi*.

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● Additional information

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Photo Gallery

海南刺灰蝶 *Acupicta hainanicum* Sugiyama, 1992 ♀

Sanya, Hainan

photograph by Zhe LIU [刘哲]